

4-SHO‘BA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AS THE FACTOR IN INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS AND EFFICIENCY IN THE FIELD OF MANAGEMENT

A.R.Akhatov, I.Q.Himmatov, Sh.I. Kadirova

Samarkand State University named after Sharof Rashidov

Ximmatov010889@gmail.com

Abstract: Nowadays, the present business organizations are determined by globalization and the appearance of the Industry concept that is mostly related to machine–people relationships, systems, and inter-machine relationships which requires a focus on the development of disposable human resources and their competencies.

Keywords: digital technology, effective management, digital transformation, technological development, increase productivity, innovative thinking.

The current business environment is primarily based on new supporting technologies such as cybernetic physical systems (CPS), adaptive robotics, virtualization, cloud technologies, etc. The importance of competitive and sustainable management is to implement the Industry concept as well as the emergence of both inter-company networks and open knowledge-based systems in organizations, where the effective acquisition, processing, storage, and sharing of key information is a predictor of success [1].

In various forms of industry, the development of digital technology based on software has caused companies to manage various initiatives to explore and exploit the opportunities that exist. Responding to this, it became very important to develop business strategies by integrating digital technology as innovation in their business.

As technology advances, it offers many effective tools and applications that managers can use when overseeing communication or managing and organizing staff workloads. With many of these business solutions, staff can train themselves and make implementation more accessible with minimal downtime and ultimate productivity [2].

If we look at the mathematical analysis of the implementation of the MCD

mathematical production function model in digital technologies for the analysis of the economic production function, today in the real economic production activity, the entire production process of an enterprise or industry with a multi-sectoral production structure consists of several small production consisting of output units. Based on the previous discussion, combined with the idea of an additional non-parametric regression model, the production function representing this input-output relationship should be a combination of several basic production functions, and artificial intelligence algorithms for its analysis process linking with becomes an effective method. That is, a model is a group of production units used to express the influence of each other. The Cobb-Douglas production function is widely used by economists due to its good economic properties. A reasonable model of the production function is assumed to be a combination of several Cobb-Douglas production functions.

$$Y=F(K,L)=F(K^{\alpha_1}L^{\beta_1},K^{\alpha_2}L^{\beta_2},\dots,K^{\alpha_m}L^{\beta_m}). \quad (1)$$

Therefore, this paper constructs a production function with the characteristics of multiple production structure, which is used to describe the input-output function relationship of a certain industry and enterprise. The specific form is shown in

$$Y = \sum_{i=1}^m A_i K^{\alpha_i} L^{\beta_i} \quad (2)$$

It is reversed from the digital form. This article calls this type of power exponential summation production function called MCD production function (Modified Cobb-Douglas Production Function). It can not only maintain some good properties of the Cobb-Douglas production function, but also improve the fitting accuracy of the production function to historical data. At the same time, it can also reflect the diversified structural characteristics of production to a certain extent [3].

The econometric form of the MCD production function is shown in

$$Y = \sum_{i=1}^m A_i K^{\alpha_i} L^{\beta_i} + \mu \quad (3)$$

In order to make the expression concise, suppose the A_i in the MCD production function is expressed as

$$A = \sum_{i=1}^m A_i, \lambda_i = A_i / A \quad (4)$$

The above hypothetical model (1) can be expressed as shown in the following formula:

$$Y = A \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i K^{\alpha_i} L^{\beta_i} + \mu \quad (5)$$

allows mathematical modeling of several economic models and serves to develop digitalization of production chains.

The main goal of disruptive technologies is to dynamize Industries. In the era of digital transformation, organizations are looking to take advantage of the efficiency revolution brought about by the management of large volumes of data,

thus benefiting from new economies of scope and scale.

Among the disruptive technologies that can increase productivity, eight stand out for their potential applicability:

- **Advanced analytics and artificial intelligence:** algorithms and high-performance computers can be used to determine patterns and perform predictive analytics to support automated learning and decision-making. This typically involves combining traditional analytics methodologies with machine learning techniques, which employ methods such as neural networks, dimensionality reduction, clustering algorithms, and deep learning networks.

- **The Internet:** sensors and actuators enable the use of smart interconnected devices that can be remotely tracked. The Internet allows “smart networks” to automate or improve the effectiveness of production and distribution processes, especially when it interacts with technologies such as advanced analytics.

- **Advanced robotics:** progress in artificial intelligence, motors, and hydraulics, computer vision and sensors are enabling robots to perform increasingly complicated tasks, with less repetitive and predictable patterns.

- **Digital platforms and cloud services:** digital or virtual platforms are spaces on the Internet that support the execution of programs in one place to meet a variety of needs. Most digital interactions take place remotely in the cloud, decreasing the need for storage and processing on local computers. Cloud computing helps computing services to be reached over a network, which reduces usage costs and facilitates the transmission of information [4].

- **Blockchain:** a blockchain is a digital ledger that works with a single decentralized, consensual register to validate information and transactions. The ledger is distributed across multiple nodes in a network and each block stores several valid records or transactions, along with information about that block and how it is linked to the previous and next block via a unique digital fingerprint [4]. As new records are developed, they are first checked and validated by the nodes in the network and then added to a new block that is connected to the chain. Moreover, if this data is kept in encrypted form, its confidentiality is assured due to the encryption key that can access it.

- **Autonomous and semi-autonomous navigation:** this encompasses vehicles operated with reduced or no human intervention. It includes trains, cars, trucks, and drones piloted by an operator. Drones can be used in different types of projects, such as underwater research, shipwreck searches, and salvage operations. They are particularly employed in offshore installations to supplement hull inspections of ships. Unmanned aircraft have been used mainly to deliver objects to remote locations and in disaster areas, as they have the advantage of being able to reach and deliver to out-of-the-way places.

- 3D printing: this belongs to the techniques known as additive manufacturing. Additive processes permit objects to be constructed by developing and consolidating layers, as opposed to subtractive techniques. Machines with the ability to print objects have attracted increasing attention in recent years. 3D printing has a great potential acceleration role to play both in the direct manufacturing of products and parts and the creation of tools.

- Augmented reality and virtual reality: technologies such as augmented reality and virtual reality are being used to reinvent the way content is created and experienced.

Immersive technologies have major implications for businesses, such as lowering production costs and lowering barriers to entry for new content creators. New technologies are unique sources of value in management, which require a clear connection between business needs and a clear vision of the solution to be implemented. The introduction of new technologies includes new communications, the entire production chain services and the reconfiguration of companies, which opens up opportunities for the development and diversification of industrial skills and the application of rapid analysis algorithms, and on this basis, the presence of operational efficiency factors in management. we can see [5].

In recent decades, research and intellectual transactions on digital transformation (DT) have been developing rapidly, and it is not surprising that there has been great interest among academics in the fields of management, economics, and the digital economy [6]. The digital transformation of business offers enormous opportunities for innovation and competitive advantage, which requires a complete rethinking of the organization: cultural, strategic and technological changes.

Digital technology plays a fundamental role, in achieving a good operational efficiency ratio within the organization and it requires the followings:

- 1) Organizational culture

Digital transformation implies the changes in the work culture and the adoption of new workflows due to the process of technological development. In this regard it is very vital to prepare employees for this transition, acquiring new technological competencies and skills to enhance efficiency.

- 2) Innovation

The company needs to involve its employees in the strategic objectives to create an appropriate organizational environment that empowers innovation processes to take place, whether they are functional, operational, or organizational.

- 3) Technology

To leverage digital transformation in management, it is essential to increase procedures through the adoption of innovative technologies that will directly influence operational efficiency, which transform into greater productivity [7].

In conclusion, we can say that the use of digital technology in organizations makes it easy to manage the work process, increase the productiveness for business people and customers to access information, and market opportunities and develop business content so that it influences people's lives. Organizations can face rapid changes that can occur due to the influence of digital technology. The existence of fast and effective business management based on data that transformed in the form of digitalization can manage a variety of policies, rules, facilities, and resources as well as help the company to perform for long-term business management.

References:

1. Katarína Stachová 1, Z. S. 1. D. C. 2. a. A. S., 2020. Use of Digital Technologies for Intensifying. Applied Science.

2. Rahmatullah, I. S. N. F. A. B., 2020. Utilization of Digital Technology for. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC & TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH.

3. Ozcam A., Ozcam D. S. Three paradoxes with the cobb-douglas production function[J] European Journal of Business and Management . 2019;11(1):245–276. [Google Scholar]

4. Anon., 2022. Digitalization for productivity. Digital technologies for a new future.

5. Axatov A.R., Ximmatov I.Q. Shaxsni harakatlari orqali identifikatsiya qilishdagi neyron tarmoqlari yordamidagi yondashuvlar . “Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar” Respublika miqyosidagi ilmiy-texnik anjuman materiallari to‘plami. – O’ZMU Jizzax filiali, 2022-yil 13-14-may. - 138-141 b.

6. A.R.Axatov. Sh.A.B. Ulug‘murodov, O.D.Primqulov. Development of algorithms for determining the breadth of digital economic change in access to open CV, open NI and PCL. “Фан, таълим ва ишлаб чиқариш интеграциясида рақамли иқтисодиёт истиқболлари” республика анжумани, ЎзМУ Жиззах филиали -6 май 2021 йил, Жиззах – 182-185 б.